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Basic concepts of criminal law applicable to certain forms of activism

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University of Coimbra

(Portugal)

July 2025

Environmental literacy in Higher Education Context for preventing radicalization in climate change activism.

WP3 Empowerment of students to prevent environmental radicalization through the development of environmental literacy and active citizenship.

OS3.3. Development of the course on the prevention of radicalization and development of environmental literacy.

When referencing this glossary, please use the following citation:

Fidalgo, S.; Lopes, D.; Graça, M.; Aragão, A. (2025). Basic concepts of criminal law applicable to certain forms of activism. Glossary from the Erasmus+ Project "ELCRA". DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17100938](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17100938)

Lay out and images: Canva.com

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Premise

Individually or collectively, climate activists can engage in a wide range of actions in different settings, which vary in visibility, disruption, and seriousness. Some examples of high visibility actions are street protests, road blockades, occupation of public or private spaces, throwing paint or substances on symbolic locations, or scaling buildings or structures. Other less visible initiatives are strikes, boycotts, lobby or campaigning against companies, industries or governments.

In some cases, the activist's conduct or its direct or indirect consequences whether voluntarily or involuntarily, knowingly or unknowingly, deliberately or negligently, may constitute a criminal offence.

Even in the absence of a specific offense targeting activism, other types of criminal charges may be brought against certain unlawful behaviours committed by activists during demonstrations or other actions. Therefore, it is important to be familiar with both the general concepts of criminal law and the specific types of offenses that may potentially apply to certain forms of climate activism.

The following general concepts of criminal law are commonly found across EU Member States. However, national variations prevail, as each Member State retains its own distinct legal traditions and features within its criminal justice system.

The 20 criminal law concepts and 16 criminal offence types have been simplified and presented in clear, accessible legal language.

This list of concepts was developed as part of the ERASMUS+ ELCRA research project on radicalization of climate activism.

Basic concepts of criminal law applicable to certain forms of activism

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General concepts

CRIMINAL LAW...

is a set of rules describing behaviours (including omissive behaviour) considered and sanctioned as criminal offences.

CRIMINAL OFFENCE ...

is a human act or omission that violates a norm of determination aimed at protecting a legal interest worthy and in need of penal protection. Behaviours that are crimes are punishable by criminal sanctions.

CRIMINAL PROCEDURAL LAW...

is the branch of law that guides and disciplines the criminal process, since the moment the suspicion of committing a crime arises until the agent is effectively convicted (or acquitted).

CRIMINAL RECORD...

is a document that contains information about an individual's criminal history. Decisions that impose penalties are recorded in the criminal record. The presentation of a clean criminal record is mandatory, for example, for the exercise of certain professions, for registration with certain professional associations or for participation in certain public competitions.

DEFENCE RIGHTS

The defendant is the holder of a set of rights, e.g. the right to be informed and to be heard; the right to remain silent; the right to legal counsel; the right to request presentation of evidence; the access to the case files, etc.

DEFENDANT...

is the person against whom an accusation is brought in a criminal proceeding. The defendant has procedural rights and duties that a suspect does not have (e.g. the right to silence).

DETENTION...

is depriving a person of liberty with the aim of presenting the detainee before the public prosecutor or the judge for being questioned.

ECOCIDE...

is understood as a qualified environmental criminal offence; it is a conduct perpetrated in the knowledge that it is highly likely to cause serious, extensive or lasting damage to the environment.

ENVIRONMENTAL CRIMES

The environment is considered a legal asset worthy and in need of criminal protection; most legal systems punish crimes against the environment. These crimes protect the fauna, the flora, the air (including the ozone layer), the acoustic environment, the soil and the water.

FORMS OF CULPABILITY (INTENT AND NEGLIGENCE)

For someone to be punished for committing a crime they must act with culpability, that is, with intent or negligence. Intent presupposes the knowledge and the will to commit the act; the agent reveals an attitude of enmity towards the law. Negligence presupposes a violation of the duty of care imposed on the subject, which led to the production of the result; the agent reveals an attitude of neglect towards the law.

GROUNDS FOR EXCLUSION OF UNLAWFULNESS

An action described in a legal type of crime will, in principle, be unlawful. But it may happen that a conduct was carried out in a factual context to which the law attributes justification for the action, meaning that the conduct will not be unlawful (e.g. self-defence).

LEGAL INTEREST ...

is a good or a value that is relevant to life in society and, therefore, must be protected by criminal law; it is an asset worthy and in need of criminal protection.

PRESUMPTION OF INNOCENCE

The defendant is presumed innocent until the final judgment that concludes with the conviction.

PREVENTIVE DETENTION...

is not a sanction but rather a measure of coercion that results in the deprivation of the defendant's freedom (arrest), which is considered necessary to prevent, for example, the danger of escape, the commitment of new crimes or the destruction of evidence.

PRINCIPLE OF LEGALITY

This principle means that there is no crime or punishment without law (*nullum crimen, nulla poena sine lege*). The principle involves four major tenets:

- 1) criminal rules must be statutory provisions;
- 2) criminal rules must be precise;
- 3) criminal rules must be binding on judges;
- 4) criminal rules must be non-retroactive.

SUSPECT...

is any person for whom there is evidence that he or she has committed or is preparing to commit a crime.

TYPES OF CRIMINAL SANCTIONS

There are three types of criminal sanctions:
main penalties; replacement penalties;
ancillary penalties.

MAIN PENALTIES...

are the ones prescribed in the Penal Code for each type of offence; the main penalties are usually imprisonment and fine.

REPLACEMENT PENALTIES...

are penalties that replace the reference penalty. For instance, imprisonment can be replaced with fine, community service, suspended sentence, etc.

ANCILLARY PENALTIES...

are penalties that may be imposed cumulatively with the main penalty (or the replacement penalty) for the fulfilment of preventative purposes. There are several ancillary penalties: e. g. prohibition of the exercise of a profession; prohibition to drive motor vehicles; disqualification from voting and from being elected, etc.

Criminal offences

ATTACK ON ROAD TRANSPORT SECURITY

Punishes anyone who violates road transport safety by destroying or rendering a communication route unusable, or by placing an obstacle to operation or circulation.

CRIMINAL DEFAMATION

Punishes anyone who makes a false statement about another person, damaging their reputation.

DAMAGE

Punishes anyone who destroys, damages or renders another person's property unusable.

When a public monument is damaged, the crime is considered more serious and the penalties provided for are also more severe.

DISOBEDIENCE

Punishes the conduct of anyone who fails to comply with a legitimate order or warrant, regularly communicated and emanating from a competent authority or official.

DISOBEYING THE ORDER TO DISPERSE A PUBLIC MEETING

Punishes anyone who does not obey an order from a competent authority to withdraw from a public meeting.

DISRUPTION OF THE FUNCTIONING OF A CONSTITUTIONAL BODY

Punishes anyone who, through disorder,
illegitimately disrupts the functioning of organs
of the State.

ILLICIT RECORDINGS AND PHOTOGRAPHS

Punishes anyone who, without consent, records a speech that is not public or photographs or films another person.

INCITEMENT TO COLLECTIVE DISOBEDIENCE

Punishes anyone who, with the intention of destroying or subverting the rule of law through violence incites collective disobedience of public order laws.

INTRODUCTION IN A PLACE CLOSED TO THE PUBLIC

Punishes anyone who, without the consent, enters or remains in a closed place and not freely accessible to the public.

KIDNAPPING

Punishes anyone who arrests another person or in any way deprives them of their liberty.

OFFENSE TO AN ORGANIZATION, SERVICE OR LEGAL PERSON

Punishes anyone who makes a false statement capable of offending the prestige that is owed to a body or service exercising public authority, to a legal person, or to a corporation.

OFFENSE TO PHYSICAL INTEGRITY

Punishes anyone who offends another
person's body or health.

OMISSION OF AID

Punishes anyone who, in case of serious need, namely caused by a disaster, accident, public calamity or situation of common danger, which endangers the life, physical integrity or freedom of another person, fails to provide the necessary assistance to the removal of danger.

PUBLIC INSTIGATION OF A CRIME

Punishes anyone who, in a public meeting, provokes or incites the commission of a crime.

SABOTAGE

Punishes anyone who destroys communication routes, public service facilities or facilities intended to supply and satisfy the population's vital needs, with the intention of destroying or subverting the rule of law.

THREAT

Punishes anyone who threatens another person with the commission of a crime, in a manner appropriate to cause fear or to harm their self-determination.

ENVIRONMENTAL LITERACY
IN HIGHER EDUCATION CONTEXT
FOR PREVENTING RADICALIZATION IN
CLIMATE ACTIVISM

Co-funded by
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2023-1-IT02-KA220-HED-000161446

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